

Beyond the Outer Tunnel: Comparisons Across Radial Regions of the Organ of Corti in the Guinea Pig Base

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Abstract. Since optical coherence tomography (OCT) has opened the door to making simultaneous motion measurements throughout the organ of Corti complex (OCC), many have focused on the area medial to the outer tunnel (the “medial region”), including the active outer hair cells (OHCs). Characterization of this active area, called the “hotspot” (Cooper, N. P., Vavakou, A., & van der Heijden, M. (2018) *Nature Communications*, 9, 3054), has been critical for understanding activity within the OCC. Exploration of motion occurring lateral of the outer tunnel (the “lateral region”), beyond the activity of the hotspot, is relevant for understanding how the OCC moves as a whole. Here, we present intra-organ of Corti motion obtained by using spectral domain OCT in the base of the Guinea Pig cochlea through the round window membrane (RWM). We obtain an approximately transverse motion pattern across the OCC’s width by taking sequential axial scans (A-scans) at different radial locations. We compare the medial and lateral regions, specifically looking at BM and the scala media (SM) border of the OCC, which includes the RL/OHC apices (medial region) and Hensen’s cells (lateral region). We find that the BM/Boettcher’s cells of the lateral region have gains and phases similar to their medial counterpart. The lateral region gain of the OCC near the Hensen’s cells is reduced compared to that of the medial RL region and has phases more like BM. We discuss the possible implications of this magnitude reduction and the influence of the fluid spaces and different cellular compositions.

INTRODUCTION

The motion of the organ of Corti complex (OCC) transduces sound from a fluid pressure into an electrical signal to be transmitted to the brain. Some of the key structures are the basilar membrane (BM), outer hair cells (OHCs), reticular lamina (RL). The BM has a thoroughly documented motion profile in response to acoustic stimuli; compressive nonlinearity re: sound pressure level (SPL) arising around the best frequency (BF) peak, and linear otherwise [1, 2]. There are also supporting cells such as Deiters’ cells (DCs), Hensen’s cells and Boettcher’s cells (BCs), which provide the general structure of the OCC.

Since the application of OCT vibrometry enabled intra-OCC motion measurements, *in vivo* OHC motion has been explored and has been found to have different behaviors of motion compared to that of the BM. Cooper *et al.* have characterized the ‘hotspot,’ the area of the largest vibrations near the OHCs, in the gerbil cochlea [3]. The OHCs are the central structure around which there is increased amplification near the best frequency (BF), as well as compressive nonlinearity extending beyond the BF peak and into the sub-BF region of frequencies [3, 4]. Motions at the OHC apices/RL region are also enlightening because they can be applied to modeling and understanding stereocilia motion, especially re: tectorial membrane. Cho and Puria have identified differences in RL motion above the different OHC rows, specifically that the RL of the first row of OHCs moves less than subsequent rows [5].

The BM, OHCs, and RL are regularly studied, but how are their movements integrated in the motion of the rest of the OCC? To examine this using a guinea pig model, we look to the outer tunnel and laterally to examine how BM and supporting cell motion differ from their medial counterparts in order to explore the total OCC motion pattern. Further, supporting cells, such as Hensen’s and Boettcher’s have different mechanical and structural properties. Here, we examine the areas of the “lateral region,” the cells and structures lateral of the OT, and their contributions to the total motion of the OCC in the guinea pig. Specifically, we compare medial and lateral BM motion, and medial OHC apices/RL region with Hensen’s cells apices.

FIGURE 1. Image of the surgical approach in juvenile guinea pigs. After a small incision, a bullostomy is made caudally to the external ear canal and the pinna, exposing the RW and first turn of the guinea pig cochlea. The gray band in the RW is the BM. The 25-35 kHz region is the most easily visible and results in a mostly transverse view of the OCC. The head of the animal is attached by dental cement to a two axis goniometer, to stabilize and allow for small angle adjustments of the OCC relative to the OCT.

METHODS

All experiments were performed in accordance with policies laid out by the Columbia University IACUC. Juvenile guinea pigs of either sex between 200-350g were anesthetized with inhalant isoflurane. A small opening in the bulla was made caudally to the external ear canal and pinna to expose the round window (RW) and the first turn of the cochlea. Figure 1 is an example of the opening made. The head was attached to a two axis goniometer to stabilize and allow precise head-angle adjustments. Cochlear condition was monitored by recording $2f_1 - f_2$ distortion product otoacoustic emissions (DPOAEs) at 50 and 70 dB sound pressure level (SPL).

Intra-OCC motion was measured via a Telesto III Spectral Domain Optical Coherence Tomography (SD-OCT) system with a sampling frequency of 130 kHz, a LSM03 5x objective lens and central wavelength of 1300nm. Sound was delivered to the ear canal via a Fostex speaker and measured with a Sokolich ultrasonic microphone sealed in the ear canal for closed-field delivery. Stimulus amplitudes were presented at 50, 60, 70, and 80 dB SPL. For motion recordings, multi-tone (zweis) stimuli containing 35 frequencies between 5-40 kHz were presented for one second [6]. During the one second stimulus presentation, the OCT recorded one-dimensional axial scans (Ascans) for vibrometry analysis. Two-dimensional scans (Bscans) were taken before and after the one second recordings to monitor overall sample movement during the recording. Ascans were taken in the approximately transverse direction, with longitudinal, radial, and transverse components of the optical axis found utilizing the program presented in Frost *et al.* 2022 [1]. A cartoon rendering of the OCC can be seen in Figure 2A, and a corresponding OCT Bscan with labelled anatomical components is in Figure 2B.

RESULTS

Motion measurements were taken at the base through the round window membrane (RWM) at an approximate best frequency (BF) of 35 kHz. The dataset presented in this manuscript for medial and lateral region comparisons is a representative dataset from Experiment GP86 runs 52 and 54. While this is only a representative dataset, additional

FIGURE 2. (A) Simplified anatomical diagram of a radial-transverse cross section of the OCC featuring relevant cells and structures. We focus on the BM medial (negative radial direction) and lateral (positive radial direction) of the outer tunnel (OT). Medial of the OT are the outer hair cells (OHCs), Deiters' cells (DCs), tectorial membrane (TM), and reticular lamina (RL). The tunnel of Corti (ToC) separates the OHCs and the inner hair cells (IHCs). The 'lateral region' contains the Hensen's cells (HCs), and Boettchers cells (BCs). (B) OCT Bscan of the radial-transverse cross-section with some structures of interest identified.

experiments have had consistent results. Longitudinal, radial, and transverse components of the optical axis were (0.2, -0.4, 0.9). The difference between these two runs was the position of the Ascans, where one was medial of the outer tunnel, and the other was lateral of the outer tunnel. For the scala tympani facing side of the OCC, we compared medial and lateral locations of the BM on either side of the outer tunnel. For the scala media side, we compared the OHC apices/RL region to the Hensen's cells apices. The medial and lateral Bscans are in Figures 3A and E. The lateral Bscan (Figure 3A) features three points of motion measurement. Lateral BM is blue, lateral Hensen's cells apices are red, and the purple is a bright region approximately $40 \mu\text{m}$ towards SM from the BM. This bright region was a recurring feature in our lateral Bscans. We believe these are the Boettcher's cells or the Boettcher's cells/Hensen's cells interface. Notably, the Boettcher's cells gain and phase are very similar to the gain and phase of the BM of the same radial location (further highlighted in Figure 4). The medial Bscan (Figure 3E) has two points of motion measurements, the medial BM (cyan) and medial OHC apices/RL region (orange). The Ascans are approximately $100 \mu\text{m}$ apart.

In Figure 3H, the phases of the Hensen's cells apices and Boettcher's cells region are plotted relative to the lateral BM. Similarly, Figure 3I presents the medial RL region phase plotted relative to the medial BM phase. Near the BF, RL region and Hensen's cells apices were in phase with the BM at their radial locations. However, the phases re: BM reached a quarter cycle phase difference at the lowest frequencies in the RL region (Figure 3I). In order to better visualize and compare the medial and lateral regions' motion, we took the 70 dB tuning curves from Figure 3 and re-plotted them in Figure 4. The BM phase across the two radial locations was approximately the same; the gain was slightly larger in the medial region than the lateral region. However, in Figure 4E, we see the SM side had a substantial difference between the medial and lateral locations. The RL region gain was much greater than that of the Hensen's cells apices. The phase was similar where visible, above approximately 15 kHz.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

When comparing the gain of the medial and lateral region, the largest difference is between the RL region and the Hensen's cells apices, highlighted in Figure 4E. This difference is to be expected, as the OHC apices/RL region are

FIGURE 3. GP86 run 52 and 54 Bscans, gain, and phase. (A) Bscan for GP86 run 54, the lateral region. White dashed line indicates the central axis of the Ascan along which vibrometry data were taken. Colored stars indicate locations in depth from which featured vibrometry data were taken (BM - blue, Boettcher's cells - purple, Hensen's cells - red). (B-D) Gain in nm/Pa (top) and phase re: ear canal pressure in cycles (bottom) from the BM (B), Boettcher's cells (C), and Hensen's cells (D). (E) Bscan for GP86 run 52, the medial region. White dashed line indicates the central axis of the Ascan along which vibrometry data were taken. Colored stars indicate locations in depth from which featured vibrometry data were taken (cyan - BM, orange - RL). (F-G) Gain in nm/Pa (top) and phase re: ear canal pressure in cycles (bottom) from the BM (F), and RL region (G). (H) Lateral Hensen's cells and Boettcher's cells phase re: lateral BM. (I) Medial RL region phase re: medial BM.

part of the hotspot while the Hensen's cells are not. Further, the fluid-filled outer tunnel separates these medial and lateral regions, which could impede the influence of the hotspot's motion on the lateral region. Within the lateral region itself (Figure 4C), gain decreases as we move from the the BM/Boettcher's towards the SM. This could be due to the mechanical properties of the Hensen's cells. The lateral region and its motion is an important factor to the overall motion of the organ of Corti. It also provides a boundary condition that can ground modeling and conceptual foundations of cochlear mechanics.

Regarding the bright area near the lateral BM (Figure 4C), it is clear that this area moved like BM despite being located approximately 40 μm towards the SM. While we cannot confidently identify what this area is, it is likely either the Hensen's cell base or the Boettcher's cells. A common obstacle during data collection in the lateral region is having both BM and internal OCC with sufficient reflectivity to detect motion out of the noise at low SPL. A benefit of this bright Boettcher's cell area that moves like the BM is the relative ease of quality recording of this area.

In gerbil, sub-BF nonlinearity is robust and seen primarily at the OHC-Deiters' cell junction, but also generally

FIGURE 4. GP86 run 52 and 54 Bscans, gain, and phases replotted to compare motion of different locations. Selected 70 dB SPL from Figure 3. (A) Bscan for GP86 run 54, the lateral region. (B) Medial and lateral BM gain (top) and phase (bottom) at 70 dB SPL. (C) Lateral BM, Boettcher's cells, and Hensen's cells region gain (top) and phase (bottom) at 70 dB SPL. (D) Bscan for GP86 run 52, the medial region. (E) Medial RL region and lateral Hensen's cells gain (top) and phase (bottom) at 70 dB SPL. (F) Medial BM and RL region gain (top) and phase (bottom) at 70 dB.

over a relatively large area. Heightened OHC motion across frequencies and its lack of representation in BM motion is still an active question of the field. However, the guinea pig base seems to have a more localized nonlinear motion pattern compared to gerbil. These details are highlighted in Figure 5, which presents different local positions in the OCC of the guinea pig base which experience sub-BF nonlinearity. The size of the hotspot and style of the sub-BF nonlinearity appear different than in gerbil [4]. In guinea pig, the highest gain and largest sub-BF nonlinearity occurs in the RL region. Further, the phase at sub-BF frequencies deviates as SPL decreases, as in Figures 5H-I, whereas BM and OHC/DC phases do not.

The lateral region is informative regarding the total motion of the OCC. The conglomeration of different cell types with different composition and mechanical properties, as well as the inclusion of fluid channels, results in a space that both moves and provides structure to the OCC. Further, understanding the difference in motion characteristics of

FIGURE 5. GP87 run 28 Bscans, gain, and phases to highlight sub-BF nonlinearity at lower sound pressure levels. (A) Bscan for GP87 run 28. White line indicates the central axis of the Ascan along which vibrometry data were taken. Colored stars indicate locations in depth from which featured vibrometry data were taken (BM - blue, central OHC - green, OHC apex - purple, RL region - red). (B) BM gain in nm/Pa (top) and phase re: ear canal in cycles (bottom). (C) Central OHC gain in nm/Pa (top) and phase re: ear canal in cycles (bottom), (D) OHC apex gain in nm/Pa (top) and phase re: ear canal in cycles (bottom). (E) RL region gain in nm/Pa (top) and phase re: ear canal in cycles (bottom). (F) BM phase for each sound pressure level relative to 80 dB SPL. (G) Central OHC phase for each sound pressure level relative to 80 dB SPL. (H) OHC apex phase for each sound pressure level relative to 80 dB SPL. (I, r, t) = (0.2, -0.3, 0.9)

this lateral region also bridges the OCC to its lateral boundary condition, the spiral ligament. Therefore, it's vital to include the lateral region when characterizing or modeling OCC mechanics as it is a large piece of the puzzle that is the OCC.

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